

European stakeholders' visions and needs for the role of Nature-based Solutions for stormwater treatment in future urban drainage systems

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Abstract

Transitioning to a water-smart society requires the involvement of different disciplines and stakeholders – e.g. academic researchers, industries, small and medium enterprises, non-governmental organisations and decision-makers. Within the EU-funded project Collaborative Urban Drainage Research Labs Communities – Co-UDlabs, one task is to identify the connections and conflicts between stakeholders and to propose adaptation strategies to support the transition of urban drainage systems within Europe, with Nature-based Solutions as an important element. Specific needs formulated for a successful implementation were collected from national policy papers and legislation in seven European countries as well as from project participants and individuals involved in the urban drainage community.

Results show that whilst awareness seems to be existing that Nature-based solutions play an important role in the transitioning process, implementation is lagging behind. Additionally, organisational and legislative structures often seem to slow down necessary change processes.

Keywords

SUDS; treatment wetlands; sponge cities; blue-green infrastructure

INTRODUCTION

Major societal and climatic challenges require transitioning from discrete examples of blue-green infrastructure to a holistic approach of integrating stormwater into the urban environment to restore water cycles (Bertrand-Krajewski 2021). Today's major challenges – exceeded planetary limits (Richardson et al. 2023), demographic change, deteriorating infrastructure, urbanization, and a desire for sustainable approaches, can be addressed by a 'water-smart society' (Water Europe 2022) or by 'water-wise behaviour' (IWA 2016). One element to reach this is combining Nature-based Solutions (NbS) with traditional infrastructure in centralised and decentralised solutions while respecting a circular economy approach, to benefit from eco-systemic services (Water SIRA 2016, Water Europe 2022). However, the different disciplines and stakeholders involved in this development – academic researchers, industries, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), NGOs and decision-makers in administration and politics–, have different visions and needs regarding the future development of urban stormwater infrastructure, which additionally vary between regions and countries.

One aim of the EU-funded project Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities (Co-UDlabs) is, therefore, to identify the connections and conflicts between disciplines and stakeholders in this process, and to propose adaptation strategies in order to support the transition of urban drainage systems (UDS) within Europe. The aim of this abstract is to present the results of the evaluation on the visions of the different disciplines and stakeholders regarding the implementation of NbS. This evaluation does not claim to be representative; however, the aim of this work is to identify and examine areas where stakeholders express needs to be fulfilled to enable this transition. The full report is available online (Tondera et al. 2022).

Furthermore, follow-up investigations are currently ongoing of how the project Co-UDlabs contributes to a progress in this field and how collaboration between different stakeholders can be improved. The general approach of Co-UDlabs consists in an innovation "starting community" that provides transnational research, with the aim to influence European regulations and practices to deliver a more

sustainable management for UDS in the face of climate change and ageing urban drainage infrastructure assets. A main part of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative Research Infrastructure (RI) that allows stakeholders in the urban drainage sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts, and then deliver those project concepts with the benefit of access to 17 large research facilities, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

METHODS

Three different sources were consulted: (i) public documents from governmental institutions and non-governmental organisations, which define or are related to a “roadmap” towards transitioning to a water smart society from the seven countries (Denmark, France, Germany, Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland, United Kingdom) involved in the project; (ii) opinions of the researchers involved in Co-UDlabs, and (iii) opinions from individuals interested in using the RIs as offered by the Co-UDlabs project. The information gathered was entered into an evaluation grid based on the themes of interest within the project. This evaluation grid served to identify the needs in different sections, and therefore contains need-based criteria and categories (Table 1). For this abstract, only entries specifically relating to the use of NbS and Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS) were evaluated, including questions of rainwater infiltration, integrated stormwater management and source-control solutions.

Currently, structured interviews with the RI providers are being held to evaluate how the research project itself contributes to dissemination and stakeholder interaction. All results will enter into a roadmap of how RI can support effective urban drainage systems transition at EU level.

RESULTS

Only for one field – Runoff pollutions in Techniques and Technologies - needs were identified by all three sources – i.e. national roadmaps, Co-UDlabs participants and (potential) RI users. They named the need for implementing and promoting NbS/integrated stormwater management to support biodiversity. All other answers presented in Table 1 showed limited similarities between the different categories. There was no entry at all with specific link to NbS for “Technical objects – Digital water solutions”, which is why this category was left out in Table 1. However, the most pertinent aspects in this category – data collection and analysis highlighted in the ‘Techniques and technologies’ criterion and management of assets and questions of costs and investment strategies in ‘Non-technical solutions’ (Tondera et al., 2022) –, are certainly of the same importance for the management of NbS as for grey infrastructure solutions.

Evaluation of national “roadmaps”

The way national regulations and frameworks have been structured and implemented results in different degrees of competences and interdependences at a local level (Tondera et al., 2022): In Denmark and the Netherlands, the general responsibilities seem to be well defined between the different actors on the national, regional and local level, whereas the situation in the other five countries is more complex. The management of stormwater and the implementation of SUDS are not always clearly defined. Overlapping responsibilities between municipalities, specific catchment-based organisations (Germany, Switzerland, England, Spain) or municipal clusters (France) and/or undefined allocation of competences lead to conflicts or neglecting of these tasks. Varying legislation in the administrative divisions (e.g. the 16 states in Germany, 17 autonomous communities and two autonomous cities in Spain, 26 cantons in Switzerland, or the four countries of the United Kingdom)

Table 1. Evaluation grid with identified needs and visions. A number in a circle means the same idea/need was expressed by different sources.

		Scientific knowledge	Techniques and technologies	Non-technical-solutions	Knowledge transfer – training of practitioners
Technical Objects	Performance				
	Asset deterioration				
Processes, impacts, risks	Urban flooding				
	Runoff pollution				
Urban services/ planning	Waterwise Cities				
Water Cycle	Water resources				
	Adaptation to climate change				
Legend		Needs expressed in the different country roadmaps	Opinions of Co-UDlabs researchers	Opinions of RI users	

add to the overall complexity. However, there is an awareness of a required change towards more sustainable development in the water sector in all countries, although the implementation into the legal framework remains on different levels and is not always clearly defined in each country. Interestingly, topics related to NbS in Table 1 were dominated by the national roadmaps. Similar requests were e.g. identified for an improved scientific knowledge on NbS and SUDS long-term performance (Assets deterioration). In terms of Techniques and technologies, the roadmaps requested a support of NbS for climate change adaptation. A better integration of stormwater management with urban planning (Waterwise Cities) and a support for applying legislation related to balanced and sustainable water resource management (Water resources) were the most requested Non-technical solutions. Knowledge transfer should e.g. focus for Waterwise Cities on training for local decision makers, professionals and planners on ecological and technical points / source control solutions. The strongest feedback was provided for the categories of Waterwise Cities and Adaptation to climate change, which shows awareness that NbS technologies can contribute to mitigating the negative effects of change. The evaluation of the organisation and legislative structure in the countries represented in our study can also be a source of slowing down innovation in the urban drainage sector; a phenomenon which was mentioned in a review by Qiao, Kristoffersson, and Randrup (2018), trying to identify challenges linked to the implementation of sustainable urban stormwater management.

Evaluation of Co-UDlabs perspectives

The Co-UDlabs perspective was obtained from the response of six project participants to the survey on the revision of the EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive and needs formulated in the project proposal. With respect to the survey, the project partners believe in line with the objectives of Co-UDlabs that the most important topics of the regulatory review are integrated approaches to better manage stormwater overflows and urban runoff. All six individuals gave the highest importance to using NbS in urban wastewater management whenever possible.

Identification of needs by the users of Research Infrastructure

A central role in transitioning to more sustainable urban water management is apparent in the focus group targeted by the Co-UDlabs project due to their potential interest in using the available RI platforms. To get their opinions of the future developments in urban drainage, we developed a survey based on the needs and vision assessment from the national roadmaps and the Co-UDlabs participants. The survey was distributed online and was also presented during a conference in Rennes, France, in June 2022. Approximately 20 participants provided feedback in Rennes, and 12 people replied to the online survey. Interestingly, transdisciplinarity was mentioned several times: There was e.g. an interest on the link between economy, science and society for integrated stormwater management (Performance - Non-technical solutions), and the request for more social science research on communication and acceptability as support for change (Runoff pollution – Scientific knowledge).

OUTLOOK

What is true for the overall results of the study – that the particular needs for Urban Drainage Systems identified by the different stakeholders are quite diverse and could not be limited to major axes (Tondera et al., 2022) –, is also true for aspects concerning NbS. However, the fact that especially national roadmaps have a strong focus on this topic shows that while awareness of the importance of a change towards blue-green infrastructure is existing, concrete actions in many cases still need to follow.

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